

The first trans-continental Networking Academy for African and European Digital Innovation Hubs.

D3.2 Structure and training material for local workshops

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Glossary and Abbreviations	
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
SME	Small and Medium-Size Enterprise
BMC	Business Model Canvas

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Executive Summary

This deliverable (D3.2) seeks to offer a complete guide for organising local training and networking workshops and meeting local DIHs needs. In total, there will be 12 local workshops in Ghana, Nigeria, Uganda and Tanzania. This document outlines the course-specific details including the course title, description, training activities and exercises that will be carried out at the local training workshops. The training is expected to be interactive and learner-centred to drive the interest of the representatives of the African DIHs. The workshops are also structured not to go over a half-day period following the recommendation included in D2.1 to run shorter events. It is envisaged that the training would take place in a hybrid form to get wider participation, and also due to the possibility of stricter COVID restrictions. Below is a list of the key areas that the workshops will cover:

1. DIH Strategy and Strategy Resources
2. DIH Business Model
3. Drafting a Preliminary Business Model for your DIH
4. The Technology Transfer Process
5. The Technology Valorisation Process
6. The Market Uptake Process
7. Bootstrapping, Revenue Models and Managerial Accounting
8. Preparing Projects for Investment and Investor Relationships
9. Building and Using a Network of Funding Sources
10. Gender Lens Innovation
11. Digital Marketing for Successful Business
12. Purpose-driven DIH

These topical areas were selected based on the opportunities for knowledge exchange from European to African DIHs as identified in WP2 under D2.1 - State of play in African DIHs: The case of Nigeria, Uganda, Ghana and Tanzania, and D2.2 - Online database with DIHs Capacity Building programmes.

1. Introduction

The Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) Capacity Building Programme aims to raise the capacities of African DIHs to better serve their own needs and long-term sustainability as well as the needs of local SMEs, start-ups and young people with an emphasis on women and people from marginalized backgrounds.

This is one of the two flagship programmes under the AfriConEU project, being the other one the Development of Transcontinental Partnerships.

The capacity building programme consists of four subprogrammes, namely:

1. Capacity building in business development models and multi-actor approach (Led by ITC);
2. Capacity building in Technology transfer of innovative technologies (IoT, AI, Big Data, etc.) (Led by PBS);
3. Capacity building on start-up's financial support (Led by DP);
4. Capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women (Led by PBS, YMH, ATBN).

The partners leading the development of the training materials do not aim to design an entirely new concept but to utilise existing materials and capitalise on achievements and lessons learned from previous and ongoing relevant initiatives. The materials developed shall be delivered in the four local innovation ecosystems targeted by the project via a variety of tools and channels. These shall consist of interactive webinars, workshops, online masterclasses and additional resources on an online repository.

This deliverable has focused on the structure and training material for the local training workshops. It is worth noting that the selected themes, structure and training approaches were designed based on the outcomes of the research and needs assessment carried out under WP2 by ATBN and ITC in the African ecosystem. Also, in order to promote a sense of ownership for the African DIH representatives who shall be trained at the workshops, the consortium will select

local facilitators with the help of the African partners. The Teaching Materials indicated in this document as PowerPoint presentations, case studies, etc., shall also be developed by the local facilitators with support from the AfriConEU consortium. Even though some materials for further reading are recommended in this document, all the Teaching Materials developed under D3.2 and links to other existing relevant materials will be uploaded into the online repository at the AfriConEU website for easy access. It is good to state that this structure and the Teaching Materials that will be developed shall be used for the implementation planning under WP4 (D4.1).

As noted in the Executive Summary, the workshops will be delivered in a blended form (face-to-face and virtual). Since the deliverable targets four African ecosystems, three (3) of the 12 workshops will be organised physically in each of the targeted cities: Akure (Nigeria), Kampala (Uganda), Kumasi (Ghana) and Dar es Salaam (Tanzania). The partners will decide on the specific themes for each country before the roll-out phase. Apart from those who meet physically at the workshop, DIH representatives from the other ecosystems will join virtually to learn and share.

To ensure continued support and improvement on African European partnerships in the DIH ecosystem, the following European DIHs have been recommended to be used as mentors to support the African DIHs that participate in the workshops. All partners, especially the European partners, may help to identify more of the European DIHs to help with the mentoring, such as:

1. Smart Agri Hubs (<https://www.smartagrihubs.eu/>)
2. Food & Bio Cluster Denmark (<https://foodbiocluster.dk/>)
3. Produtech (<http://www.produtech.org/>)
4. Among others.

Also, please take into consideration that the analysis of this document should be complemented with the future analysis of D3.1 Capacity Building Flagship Programme, as it will include the overall structure of the capacity building programme. Additionally, and because the responsible partners for elaborating D3.2

(and even D3.1 and D3.3) are not the only ones who are going to implement the AfriconEU programmes, it was decided to keep the materials open, flexible and adaptable to fit various methods and approaches.

2. Business Development Models and Multi Actor Approach

2.1 Workshop 1: DIH Strategy and Strategy Resources

2.1.1 Overview

This workshop aims to explore the multi-sidedness and the indirectness of the DIH business model, its service portfolio and configure it to a DIH according to the overall strategic vision of the DIH. Overall, this workshop aims to support DIHs in setting up their strategy and its importance to DIHs.

Topics to be discussed:

- Defining strategy;
- Strategic planning;
- Strategy formulation;
- Phases of the strategy process;
- Strategy development tools.

2.1.2 Learning Objectives

By the end of this course, participants should be able to:

- Understand what strategy is and what the purpose of strategic planning is;
- Know how to use at least one strategy development tool;
- Build a DIH's strategy;
- Implementing the strategy.

2.1.3 Delivery Methods

- Lecture;
- Presentation;
- Group activity;
- Questions and answers.

2.1.4 Teaching Materials

- PowerPoint presentation;

- Strategy development tools.

2.1.5 Activity Plan

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Session 1: Defining Strategy: From concept to planning and implementation		
Motivate	5	Video about DIHs
House Keeping	5	Introduction, timetable, principles for an effective training experience
Topic 1-3: Defining Strategy, Strategic Planning, Strategy Formulation	50	Lecture, presentation
Total Time for Session	60	
Break	5	
Session 2: Strategy Development process		
Motivate	10	Brainstorming about strategy
House Keeping	5	Introduction, timetable, what participants will get
Topic 1: Phase of the strategy process	45	Lecture, presentation
Break	5	
Topic 2: Strategy Development Tools	30	Lecture, presentation
Learning activity: Build a strategy with different tools: SWOT analysis, Balanced Scorecard, PEST analysis	45	participants divided into small groups to complete an assigned task
Time for answers and questions	10	
Conclusions	5	
Total Time for Session	155	
Total Time for workshop	215	

2.1.6 Assessment

At the end of the course, each participant should be able to address the following questions:

1. What is the DIH strategy?
2. Why is it beneficial for DIH to have conducted and implemented the strategy?
3. Who should build a DIH strategy?
4. How can you use strategy tools?

2.1.7 Training Exercises

Use the following tools to build your business strategy (they shall be uploaded on the online repository):

1. SWOT Analysis template;
2. Balanced Scorecard;
3. PEST analysis sheet.

2.2 Workshop 2: DIH Business Model

2.2.1 Overview

In this workshop, participants will increase their knowledge base and structure of thinking about business models by linking strategy and business modelling, understanding the importance of business modelling for DIHs and the path to sustainability, and learning how a DIH can define its Business Model based on the offered service portfolio.

Topics to be discussed:

- Linking Strategy and Business Modelling;
- Understanding the importance of Business Modelling for DIHs and the path to sustainability;
- DIHs service and multi-actor approach;
- A business model based on the offered service portfolio.

2.2.2 Learning Objectives

By the end of this course, participants should be able to:

- Link strategy and business model;
- Understand the importance of business modelling for DIHs and the path to sustainability;
- Define DIHs Business Model based on the offered service portfolio;
- Define service portfolio.

2.2.3 Delivery Methods

- Lecture;
- Presentation;
- Group activity;
- Questions and answers.

2.2.4 Teaching Materials

- PowerPoint presentations;
- Case studies.

2.2.5 Activity Plan

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Session 1 Title: Business models		
Motivate	5	Video/ice breaker about business models
House Keeping	5	Introduction, timetable, principles for an effective training experience
Topic 1: Linking Strategy and Business Modelling	15	Lecture, presentation, etc
Learning activity: Is the business model a part of the strategy?	15	Brainstorming & presenting the group results
Topic 2: Understand the importance of business modelling for DIHs and the path to sustainability	45	
Learning activity: Why should a DIH operate with a specific business model?	15	Brainstorming & presenting the group results
Total Time for Session	100	
Break	15	
Session 2 Title: A business model based on the offered service portfolio		
Motivate	5	What participants will get from session 2
House Keeping	5	Introduction, timetable
Topic 1: DIHs service and multi-actor approach	15	Lecture, presentation – short introduction about service portfolio
Learning activity: What is the multi-actor approach? Why should beneficiaries be involved in the design of DIH programs?	15	Brainstorming & presentation about offered service portfolio
Topic 2: DIHs service and multi-actor approach	45	Lecture, presentation

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Break	5	
Topic 3: A business model based on the offered service portfolio	45	Lecture, presentation
Learning activity: What is the connection between services and business models?	15	Brainstorming & presentation
Case study	15	A case study from Food & Bio Cluster Denmark
Time for answers and questions	10	
Conclusions	5	
Total Time for Session	180	
Total Time for workshop	295	

2.2.6 Assessment

At the end of the course, each participant should be able to address the following questions:

1. What is the business model?
2. Why is it beneficial to link strategy and business model?
3. Who can be offered DIH services?
4. How can DIH conduct a business model based on offered DIH services?

2.2.7 Training Exercise

Use the value proposition tool to demonstrate how customers (start-ups, youth, etc) connect with your DIH (it shall be uploaded on the online repository):

- Value Proposition Template.

2.3 Workshop 3: Draft a Preliminary Business Model for your DIHs

2.3.1 Overview

In this workshop, the participants will be introduced to Business Models development and two tools: Lean Canvas and Business Model Canvas (BMC).

Topics to be discussed:

- What's the BMC?

- Step by step guide
- What's the Lean Canvas?
 - Step by step guide

2.3.2 Learning Objectives

By the end of this course, participants should be able to:

- Understand business modelling;
- Design a business model.

2.3.3 Delivery Methods

- Lecture;
- Presentation;
- Group activity;
- Case studies;
- Questions and answers.

2.3.4 Teaching Materials

- PowerPoint presentations;
- Case studies

These materials shall be prepared by local facilitators and uploaded onto the online repository.

2.3.5 Activity Plan

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Session 1 Title: Business Model Canvas		
Motivate	5	Video/ice breaker
House Keeping	5	Introduction, timetable, principles for an effective training experience
Topic 1: BMC	30	Lecture, presentation – what is BMC
Topic 2: Step by step guide	45	Lecture, presentation – how to conduct BMC
Learning activity: Draw a BMC for your DIH with the template given	30	Individual work, each display on the wall, walk and observe activity by the whole group
Break	10	

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Presentation & Feedback	45	
Questions & answers	15	
Total Time for Session	185	
Session 2 Title: Lean Canvas		
Motivate	5	Video/ice breaker
House Keeping	5	Expectations, timetable
Topic 1: BMC	30	Lecture, presentation – what is BMC
Topic 2: Step by step guide	20	Lecture, presentation – how to conduct BMC
Learning activity: Convert the BMC drawn in the earlier activity into a lean canvas	30	Individual work, each display on the wall, walk and observe activity by the whole group
Break	10	
Presentation & Feedback	45	
Questions & answers	15	
Total Time for Session	130	
Total Time for Course	315	

2.3.6 Assessment

At the end of the course, each participant should be able to address the following questions:

1. What are business modelling tools?
2. Why is it beneficial to conduct business modelling?
3. Who can conduct business modelling?
4. How can you use business modelling tools for developing business models?

2.3.7 Training Exercises

Use the following tools to design a business model for your DIH (these shall be uploaded on the online repository.)

1. BMC Template;
2. Lean Canvas.

3. Technology transfer of innovative technologies

3.1 Workshop 4: The Technology Transfer Process

3.1.1 Overview

This workshop aims at helping DIHs to explore the concept of technology transfer (IoT, AI, Big data, etc.), its benefits and the legal framework to protect the technology transfer. It covers the aspects of the transfer chain including transfer concept, technical analysis, and how to create value to innovate.

Topics to be discussed:

- Concept of technology transfer;
- Characterizing features of technology transfer;
- Technology transfer mechanisms;
- Motivations for technology transfer;
- Benefits of technology transfer;
- Legal framework for technology transfer;
- Technology transfer offices;
- Overview of the technology transfer process;
- First stage: create value to innovate;
- Second stage: develop the partnership.

3.1.2 Learning Objectives

By the end of this course, participants should be able to:

- Formulate an action plan to transfer a technology (IP) from lab to market;
- Get a comprehensive overview of the technology transfer process;
- Establish the benefits of technology transfer and the motivation to do it.

3.1.3 Delivery Methods

- Seminar-style presentations;
- Group discussions;
- Hands-on work: Technology Assessment Dashboard; Case studies; The Technology Transfer Canvas, etc.;

- Take home tasks to complete before/ after the workshop.

3.1.4 Teaching Materials

- PowerPoint presentations;
- Examples from case studies;
- Canvases for technology transfer;
- Best practical examples from DIH.

These materials shall be prepared by local facilitators and uploaded onto the online repository.

3.1.5 Activity Plan

The following part is merely illustrative. Workshop lecturers/ organisers are free to adapt the structure of the workshop to better fit the market and participants needs, as well as according to the topic needs (i.e. there might be topics that require more time than others, which should be addressed when the final structure is designed).

At this stage, it is foreseen that each topic will include both theoretical and practical approaches.

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Workshop Title: The Technology Transfer Process		
Motivate	5	Ice breaker
House Keeping	10	Expectations, timetable, how the course will run, etc
Topic 1: Concept of technology transfer	20	Delivery will include seminar-style presentation; group discussions; hands-on work, etc.)
Topic 2: Characterizing features of technology transfer	20	
Topic 3: Technology transfer mechanisms	20	
Topic 4: Motivations for technology transfer	20	
Topic 5: Benefits of technology transfer	20	
Break	25	
Topic 6: Legal framework for technology transfer	20	Delivery will include seminar-style presentation; group discussions; hands-on work, etc.)
Topic 7: Technology transfer offices	20	
Topic 8: Overview of the technology transfer process	20	

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Topic 9: First stage: create value to innovate	20	
Topic 10: Second stage: develop the partnership	20	
Total Time for the workshop	240	4 hours (for example a whole morning)

3.1.6 Assessment

At the end of the course, each participant should be able to address the following issues:

1. What are the key features of a technology transfer Action Plan?
2. What are technology assessment dashboards and how can they be used?
3. What are the different pathways for technology valorisation?
4. How might a DIH support a spin-off creation?

3.1.7 Training Exercise

Participants will be invited to engage in the following exercise:

Think of a model technology or software that is being worked on at your hub or start-up. Write down the benefits you imagine could be derived from applying the concept of technology transfer to it.

3.2 Workshop 5: The Technology Valorisation Process

3.2.1 Overview

This workshop builds on the concept of technology transfer discussed in workshop 4. It focuses on the technology transfer process with emphasis on value proposition, market analysis, the capacity of the research team and the partners involved. It also highlights the relevance of the time of market entry and adhering to a strong strategic plan, patenting and proof of concept.

Topics to be discussed:

- The technology identification phase;
- Results of R&D activity;

- Invention disclosure;
- The technology assessment phase;
- Factors to make the right decisions;
- The value proposition of the technology;
- Market analysis;
- Time of market entry;
- Protection strength;
- The capacity of the research team;
- Pathways to transfer technology;
- Partners in technology transfer;
- Technology transfer strategic plan;
- Market validation;
- The technology protection phase;
- Overview of intellectual property rights;
- Getting the technology protected by patenting;
- The patenting process in a nutshell;
- The technology readiness phase;
- Bridging the gap towards the market;
- Development and proof of concept.

3.2.2 Learning Objectives

By the end of this course, participants should be able to:

- Know the fundamentals of technology identification, assessment, protection and maturation;
- Understand the patenting process;
- Establish technology readiness and identify the right time of market entry.

3.2.3 Delivery Methods

- Seminar-style presentations;
- Group discussions;

- Hands-on work: Technology Assessment Dashboard; Case studies; The Technology Transfer Canvas, etc.;
- Take home tasks to complete before/ after the workshop.

3.2.4 Teaching Materials

- PowerPoint presentations;
- Examples from case studies;
- Canvases for technology transfer;
- Best practices examples from DIH.

These materials shall be prepared by local facilitators and uploaded onto the online repository.

3.2.5 Activity Plan

The following part is merely illustrative. Workshop lecturers/ organisers are free to adapt the structure of the workshop to better fit the market and participants needs, as well as according to the topic needs (i.e. there might be topics that require more time than others, which should be addressed when the final structure is designed).

At this stage, it is foreseen that each topic will include both theoretical and practical approaches.

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Workshop Title: The Technology Valorisation Process		
Motivate	5	Ice breaker
House Keeping	5	Expectations, timetable, how the course will run, etc
Topic 1: The technology identification phase	10	Delivery will include seminar-style presentation; group discussions; hands-on work, etc.)
Topic 2: Results of R&D activity	10	
Topic 3: Invention disclosure	10	
Topic 4: The technology assessment phase	10	
Topic 5: Factors to make the right decisions	10	

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Topic 6: The value proposition of the technology	10	
Topic 7: Market analysis	10	
Topic 8: Time of market entry	10	
Topic 9: Protection strength	10	
Topic 10: Capacity of the research team	10	
Break	20	
Topic 11: Pathways to transfer technology	10	Delivery will include seminar-style presentation; group discussions; hands-on work, etc.)
Topic 12: Partners in technology transfer	10	
Topic 13: Technology transfer strategic plan	10	
Topic 14: Market validation	10	
Topic 15: The technology protection phase	10	
Topic 16: Overview of intellectual property rights	10	
Topic 17: Getting the technology protected by patenting	10	
Topic 18: The patenting process in a nutshell	10	
Topic 19: The technology readiness phase	10	
Topic 20: Bridging the gap towards the market	10	
Topic 21: Development and proof of concept	10	
Total Time for the workshop	240	4 hours (for example a whole morning)

3.2.6 Assessment

At the end of the course, each participant should be able to address the following issues:

1. What are the key features of a technology transfer Action Plan?
2. What are technology assessment dashboards and how can they be used?
3. What are the different pathways for technology valorisation?

4. How might DIH support spin-off creation?

3.2.7 Training Exercise

Participants will be invited to engage in the following exercise:

“Use the following tool to create the value proposition for the technology transfer (they shall be uploaded on the online repository):

- [Technology transfer canvas by The Transfer institute](#)”

3.3 Workshop 6: The Market Uptake Process

3.3.1 Overview

This workshop aims to deepen and share competencies, expertise and knowledge on technology transfer with emphasis on the market uptake process. It covers details of drawing up agreements or contracts with identified partners in the technological transfer process. It also explores the monitoring mechanisms that are essential to check the technology transfer process.

Topics to be discussed:

- The engagement phase;
- The process for locating technology partners;
- The engagement process with technology;
- The deal-making and negotiation phase;
- The contracting phase;
- Overview of technology transfer contracts;
- License agreement;
- Spin-offs (start-up creation);
- The monitoring phase;
- Monitoring actions.

3.3.2 Learning Objectives

By the end of this course, participants should be able to:

- Develop a partnership engagement strategy;

- Understand the fundamentals of negotiation, contracting;
- Develop and implement technology transfer monitoring actions.

3.3.3 Delivery Methods

- Seminar-style presentations;
- Group discussions;
- Hands-on work: Technology Assessment Dashboard; Case studies; The Technology Transfer Canvas, etc.;
- Take home tasks to complete before/ after the workshop.

3.3.4 Teaching Materials

- PowerPoint presentations;
- Examples from case studies;
- Canvases for technology transfer;
- Best practices examples from DIH.

3.3.5 Activity Plan

The following part is merely illustrative. Workshop lecturers/ organisers are free to adapt the structure of the workshop to better fit the market and participants needs, as well as according to the topic needs (i.e. there might be topics that require more time than others, which should be addressed when the final structure is designed). At this stage, it is foreseen that each topic will include both theoretical and practical approaches.

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Workshop Title: The Market Uptake Process		
Motivate	5	Ice breaker
House Keeping	10	Expectations, timetable, how the course will run, etc
Topic 1: The engagement phase	20	Delivery will include seminar-style presentation; group discussions; hands-on work, etc.)
Topic 2: The process for locating technology partners	20	
Topic 3: The engagement process with technology	20	
Topic 4: The deal-making and negotiation phase	20	

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Topic 5: The contracting phase	20	
Break	25	
Topic 6: Overview of technology transfer contracts	20	Delivery will include seminar-style presentation; group discussions; hands-on work, etc.)
Topic 7: License agreement	20	
Topic 8: Spin-offs (startup creation)	20	
Topic 9: The monitoring phase	20	
Topic 10: Monitoring actions	20	
Total Time for the workshop	240	4 hours (for example a whole morning)

3.3.6 Assessment

At the end of the course, each participant should be able to address the following issues:

1. What are the key features of a technology transfer Action Plan?
2. What are technology assessment dashboards and how can they be used?
3. What are the different pathways for technology?
4. How might DIH support spinoff creation?

3.3.7 Training Exercise

Participants will be invited to engage in the following exercise:

“Use the following tool to create the partnership engagement phase for the technology transfer as identified in workshop 4 (they shall be uploaded on the online repository):

- [Technology transfer canvas by The Transfer institute](#)

4. Building on start-up's financial support

4.1 Workshop 7: Bootstrapping, Revenue Models and Managerial Accounting

4.1.1 Overview

Understanding the fundamentals of revenue models and financial control, along with an overview of the bootstrapping method of funding a project or business. This will incorporate 4 major components. First an overview discussion of finances and bootstrapping. Second, major business models and revenue streams are available to a project. Third, cost centres within operations, including a discussion of fixed and variable costs, and categorization into value-added, non-value added and waste expenses. Finally, bringing the principles together into a discussion of managerial accounting overall.

Topics to be discussed:

- An overview of financial controls and management;
- Fundamental concepts for the course;
- Bootstrapping as a funding mechanism;
- Overview of major business models;
- Overview of major revenue streams;
- Applying business models and revenue streams to DIHs;
- Operational cost centres;
- Fixed and variable costs;
- Value-added, non-value added and waste costs;
- Managerial accounting process and examples.

4.1.2 Learning Objectives

By the end of this course, participants should be able to:

- Develop a business model incorporating cost centres and revenue streams;
- Perform managerial accounting to reduce costs;
- Plan operations for a business, “with an eye” towards bootstrapping;

- Provide training to support projects in bootstrapping and managerial accounting.

4.1.3 Delivery Methods

- Seminar-style presentations;
- [Hands-on work with Realia](#);
- Canvas-style filling in of information from participant projects;
- Take home tasks to complete between sessions.

4.1.4 Teaching Materials

- Presentations;
- Example financial descriptions from case studies;
- Canvases for revenue models, cost centres and managerial accounting;
- Best practice examples from DIHs.

4.1.5 Activity Plan

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Session 1: Title: Finances, Bootstrapping and Business Models		
Motivate	5	Ice breaker
Housekeeping	10	Expectations, timetable, how the course will run, etc
Topic 1: Fundamentals of financial controls and management, the definition of bootstrapping	40	
Break	5	
Topic 2: Overview of major business models and revenue streams	60	
Group Activity	15	Brainstorming to fill in canvases & Presentation to group
Break	15	
Ice Breaker	15	What information are we missing? Where can we get it? (Becomes take-home material)
Topic 3: Best practice revenue streams and models for DIHs	45	
Total Time for Session	210	
Session 2 Title: Cost Centres and Managerial Accounting		
Motivate	20	Review of take-home material

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
House Keeping	10	Expectations, timetable, how the course will run, etc
Topic 1: Review of previous material, introduction to cost centres as a concept	30	
Break	5	
Topic 2: Categorizing cost centres into: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fixed and variable costs; - Value-added, non-value-added, waste. 	60	
Group Activity	30	Isolating and categorizing costs centres for revenue streams and business models presented
Break	15	
Ice Breaker	10	Begin to analyse potential cuts
Topic 3: Introduction to managerial accounting methods, examples using real-world examples	60	
Total Time for Session	210	
Total Time for workshop	420	

4.1.6 Assessment

At the end of the course, each participant should be able to address the following questions:

1. What is bootstrapping?
2. What is managerial accounting?
3. How can you differentiate between kinds of cost centres?
4. What business model and revenue stream do I use?
5. How can I make my work more efficient?

4.1.7 Training Exercise

Participants will be invited to engage in the following exercise:

“Working as teams from each DIH, perform the following tasks for your DIH (use a pen to draw two lines to divide a flipchart paper into 4):

1. *In the first column, make a list of the major financial controls or policies you operate with as a hub;*
2. *In column 2, write down your revenue streams as a hub:*

3. *In the third column, list your cost of operation;*
4. *In column 4, draw your business model."*

4.2 Workshop 8: Preparing projects for investment and investor relationships

4.2.1 Overview

Documenting and promoting a project to strengthen financing efforts and an overview of terms, interests and needs from investors. This will include an overview of how to pitch and promote a project, along with key quantitative metrics and tools to be included. Some of the key metrics will include market analysis, financial and revenue forecasts and other KPIs including impact metrics as appropriate. Using the lens of an investor, samples of standard term sheets and funding relationships, notable grants, debt and equity will be shown to participants. Investor motivations and interests, along with specialized kinds of investors, will be covered.

Topics to be discussed:

- Basics of pitching;
- Fundamentals of a business plan;
- Essential metrics to be included;
- Grants, debt, and equity;
- Investor expectations;
- Specialized kinds of investors;
- Basics of a term sheet.

4.2.2 Learning Objectives

By the end of this course, participants should be able to:

- Develop key metrics needed to prepare a project for financing;
- Present a project to funders to seek support;
- Define appropriate funding mechanisms for a project;
- Pitch a project.

4.2.3 Delivery Methods

- Seminar-style presentation;
- Hands-on work with metrics and canvases;
- Direct application in the form of a pitch.

4.2.4 Teaching Materials

- Presentations;
- Hands-on examples;
- Lexicons and glossaries of key terms and formulas.

4.2.5 Activity Plan

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Session 1 Title: How to Pitch a Project		
Motivate	5	Ice breaker
Housekeeping	10	Expectations, timetable, how the course will run, etc
Topic 1: What to include in a pitch	30	
Break	5	
Topic 2: Essential information in a business plan	60	
Group Activity	15	Filling in fundamentals of a business plan in groups
Break	15	
Ice Breaker	10	Elevator pitching
Topic 3: Key business metrics to be included: Market size, revenue forecasts, financial data, ESG, traction	60	
Total Time for Session	210	
Session 2 Title: How investors work		
Motivate	10	Refined elevator pitching
House Keeping	10	Expectations, timetable, how the course will run, etc
Topic 1: Grants vs debt vs equity as funding structures	45	
Break	5	
Topic 2: What investors look for Specialized investors: CVC, serial entrepreneurs, impact investors	60	
Group Activity	10	Group discussion: Fitting investor types to projects
Break	15	

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Ice Breaker	5	Presentation of discussions
Topic 3: Fundamentals of a term sheet	45	
Total Time for Session	210	
Total Time for Course	420	

4.2.6 Assessment

At the end of the course, each participant should be able to address the following questions:

1. What are investors looking for?
2. What metrics can demonstrate that?
3. How do investors vary in their interests and goals?
4. What are the different uses of debt, equity, and grant financing?
5. What are the key elements of a term sheet?

4.2.7 Training Exercises

1. *Using the pitch deck template on the online repository, prepare a pitch for your DIH to request funding from an investor. You will have 5 mins to pitch this to pseudo investors (other participants and the facilitator) for feedback;*
2. *Connect with a DIH with a similar business model as yours and compare your pitch deck with theirs. What are the similarities and differences? Where can you improve?*

4.3 Workshop 9: Building and using a network of funding sources

4.3.1 Overview

Understanding innovation and project lifecycles and the role of different funding sources throughout that process. The process of mapping and reaching out to actors in an ecosystem. Developing a DIH as a reference point for different funding methods and meeting the needs of different kinds of investors and funding sources.

This includes events and programs that will support matchmakings such as incubation, acceleration, scouting, pitch/demo events, or bootcamps. Connecting with the program on investor relationships, the workshop will include an introduction to the interests and needs of funding sources.

Topics to be discussed:

- Innovation lifecycle;
- Key funding sources at different points;
- Features of those funding sources;
- Mapping an innovation ecosystem;
- Needs of financial actors;
- Roles played by DIHs;
- How to pay for them.

4.3.2 Learning Objectives

By the end of this course, participants should be able to:

- Describe funding sources within their innovation ecosystem;
- Match financing sources to project needs;
- Describe the role of DIHs as reference points;
- Identify key roles and activities for DIHs as matchmaking.

4.3.3 Delivery Methods

- Seminar-style lecture;
- Best practices;
- Brainstorming;
- Hands-on work with canvases;
- Take-home material (participants will be asked to map their innovation ecosystem between sessions).

4.3.4 Teaching Materials

- Presentation;
- Best practice examples;

- Canvases and similar forms.

4.3.5 Activity Plan

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Session 1 Title: The Funding Landscape		
Motivate	5	Ice breaker
House Keeping	10	Expectations, timetable, how the course will run, etc
Topic 1: Innovation lifecycles	30	
Break	5	
Topic 2: Funding sources and needs over an innovation lifecycle	60	
Group Activity	15	Identifying project needs among those supported
Break	15	
Ice Breaker	10	Contextualizing project needs
Topic 3: What is an innovation ecosystem? How do you map it?	60	
Total Time for Session	210	
Session 2 Title: DIHs as a Reference Point		
Motivate	20	Presentation of ecosystem maps as take-home material
House Keeping	10	Expectations, timetable, how the course will run, etc
Topic 1: Varied needs of funding sources	30	
Break	5	
Topic 2: Roles played by DIHs between financing and projects, examples and best practices	60	
Group Activity	15	Group discussion: Project ideas for participant hubs
Break	15	
Ice Breaker	10	Presentation of discussions
Topic 3: How various activities are funded, examples and best practices	45	
Total Time for Session	210	
Total Time for Course	420	

4.3.6 Assessment

At the end of the course, each participant should be able to address the following questions:

1. How do the financial needs of an innovative project evolve over its lifecycle?

2. What are the key funding sources in my ecosystem?
3. How can I map them?
4. What do they need?
5. What role can DIHs play, and how can it be paid for?

4.3.7 Training Exercises

Participants will be invited to engage in the following exercise:

“This exercise seeks to identify your key stakeholders, how your projects are funded and the steps you take as a hub to sustain the project beyond the funding stage.

1. *Who are the key stakeholders in your ecosystem?*
2. *On a flip chart, draw the key relationships between the stakeholders and your operational activities.*
3. *Discuss with your team and write down the sustainability models you use at your DIH.”*

5. Digital and entrepreneurial skills development

5.1 Workshop 10: Gender Lens Innovation

5.1.1 Overview

In this workshop, participants shall be introduced to gender lens thinking and tools. The goal of the webinar is to help hub leaders build programs that contribute to the decrease in gender inequality. Specifically, we will look at how to market programmes to the female audience, how to design programs around the unique needs of women and how to get access to relevant kinds of funding.

Topics to be discussed:

- Marketing with a gender lens;
- Gender lens Design;
- Gender lens finance.

5.1.2 Learning Objectives

By the end of this course, participants should be able to:

- Explain how gender lens innovation can be used to design system-level solutions to gender inequality;
- Understand how capital allocation contributes to gender inequality and the emerging tools and approaches in gender lens finance;
- Design an intervention using women-centric design.

5.1.3 Delivery Methods

- Seminar-style presentations;
- Group discussions;
- Hands-on work;
- Take home tasks to complete before/ after the workshop;
- Case studies;
- Work in groups.

5.1.4 Teaching Materials

- PowerPoint presentations;
- Examples from case studies;
- Useful templates;
- Best practical examples from DIH.

These materials shall be prepared by local facilitators and uploaded onto the online repository.

5.1.5 Activity Plan

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Workshop Title: Gender Lens Innovation		
Motivate	5	Video/ice breaker
House Keeping	10	Expectations, timetable, how the course will run, etc
Topic 1: Marketing with a gender lens (What is a gender lens approach and how is it relevant to marketing?)	50	Lecture/brainstorm/activity/ individual task/ presentation, etc
Break	15	
Topic 2: Gender-lens design (Intro to human-centred design, including social entrepreneurs' definition; as well as add a gender lens to human-centred design)	50	Lecture/brainstorm/activity/ individual task/ presentation, etc
Learning Activity: What is Gender-lens design?	20	Brainstorming & Presentation
Break	30	
Topic 3: Gender-lens finance (Intro to Gender Len Investment - Goals, history, the need, basic concepts, example of funds)	40	Lecture/brainstorm/activity/ individual task/ presentation, etc
Learning Activity: Where are the opportunities for gender lens investing in women's financial inclusion?	20	Brainstorming & Presentation
Total Time for Workshop	240	4h (for example, a whole morning)

5.1.6 Assessment

At the end of the course, each participant should be able to address the following questions:

1. What is Gender Lens?
2. Why is it beneficial to attract more women to DIH programs, helping achieve DIH impact goals around diversity?

3. How to apply gender lens design to my program?
4. What kind of funding is available for my women stakeholders?

5.1.7 Training Exercise

Participants will be invited to engage in the following exercise:

“Hub level activity: Together with your team, analyse your DIH’s activities with the following questions to see if you are gender-wise. You shall be asked by your facilitator to share outcomes of your discussions with the whole class.”

Culture

Does your organisation serve all genders by:

1. *Holding board meetings, retreats, staff meetings etc at times when people of all genders are able to participate fully?*
2. *Offering family-friendly benefits, such as family leave, job-sharing, family violence leave, and childcare?*
3. *Training board and staff members to recognise and address discrimination, equity and language bias regarding gender, race, age, disability and sexual orientation? Do your policies adequately and appropriately address sexual harassment, domestic violence, discrimination, and protections for those expressing grievances?*
4. *Seeking appropriate gender-related expertise or collaborations?*
5. *Taking into account how racial, ethnic and cultural dynamics affect the interests and needs of specific groups of women and girls?*

Governance

Does your organisation include women and girls as active decision-makers by:

1. *Ensuring they are adequately represented in staff, executive and board leadership positions?*
2. *Encouraging their participation in strategic planning, program planning, staff development and evaluation?*

- 3. Demonstrating a commitment to women and girls in both budgeting and expenditures? For example, do you provide equitable and appropriate compensation with the opportunity for professional growth?*

5.2 Workshop 11: Digital Marketing for Successful Businesses

5.2.1 Overview

This workshop will support participants working in brand, marketing, digital media, product management and as well as entrepreneurs to learn how to develop digital marketing strategies that will provide for growth and customer engagement.

Topics to be discussed:

- Digital Marketing Plan;
- Current trends and practices;
- Digital Marketing Tools;
- Online & Offline Marketing;
- Customer Engagement;
- Influencer Marketing.

5.2.2 Learning Objectives

By the end of this course, participants should be able to:

- Explore current trends in digital marketing, tools and best practices;
- Learn how to combine online and offline marketing;
- Promote and expand their businesses online;
- Apprentice how to develop an effective digital marketing plan;
- Reinforce customer engagement.

5.2.3 Delivery Methods

- Seminar-style presentations;
- Group discussions;
- Hands-on work;

- Take home tasks to complete before/ after the workshop;
- Case studies;
- Work in groups.

5.2.4 Teaching Materials

- PowerPoint presentations;
- Examples from case studies;
- Useful templates;
- Best practical examples from DIH.

These materials shall be prepared by local facilitators and uploaded onto the online repository.

5.2.5 Activity Plan

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Workshop Title: Digital Marketing for Successful Businesses		
Session 1 Title: Digital Marketing		
Motivate	5	Video/ice breaker
House Keeping	5	Set guidelines, Expectations, explain timetable, how the course will run, etc
Topic 1: Digital Marketing Plan	25	Lecture/brainstorm/ activity/ individual task/ presentation, etc
Break	5	
Topic 2: Digital Marketing Tools	30	Lecture/brainstorm/ activity/ individual task/ presentation, etc
Learning Activity: List the digital marketing tools you know or have used before.	15	Brainstorming & Presentation
Break	15	
Ice Breaker	5	Group activity
Topic 3: Customer Engagement	15	Lecture/brainstorm/ activity/ individual task/ presentation, etc
Total Time for Session	120	
Session 2 Title: From Offline to Online		
Motivate	5	Video/ice breaker
House Keeping	5	Set guidelines, Expectations, explain timetable, how the course will run, etc
Topic 1: Online & Offline Marketing	20	Lecture/brainstorm/ activity/ individual task/ presentation, etc

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Break	5	
Topic 2: Current trends and practices	25	Lecture/brainstorm/ activity/ individual task/presentation/sharing practices, etc
Learning Activity: In groups of three, list what you have observed in the marketing space recently.	15	Brainstorming & Presentation
Break	15	
Ice Breaker	5	Group activity
Topic 3: Influencer Marketing	25	Lecture/brainstorm/ activity/ individual task/ presentation/ work in groups, etc
Total Time for Session	120	
Total Time for Workshop	240	4h (for example, a whole morning)

5.2.6 Assessment

At the end of the course, each participant should be able to address the following questions:

1. Why is Digital Marketing important for the growth of the business?
2. How Digital Marketing can increase the profitability and growth of the business?
3. How to use digital tools more effectively?
4. How can you influence your clients through Digital Marketing?

5.2.7 Training Exercise

Participants will be invited to come up with a digital marketing plan for their DIH using the digital marketing plan template as found on the online repository.

5.3 Workshop 12: Purpose-driven DIH

5.3.1 Overview

Through this workshop participants will become aware of the ecosystem of African DIHs, particularly the key challenges they face and how to overcome them. Moreover, participants will be supported to set the scene and define their activity with the explanation of their purpose and role, as well as the description of their

processes. There will also be an important focus on project management and strategic planning.

Topics to be discussed:

- **Setting the scene for DIH**
 - Purpose
 - Role
 - Processes

- **DIH activity**
 - Key business challenges
 - Project management
 - Strategic planning

5.3.2 Learning Objectives

By the end of this course, participants should be able to;

- Define their DIH purpose and role to better communicate it outdoors;
- Identify their core processes and how to perform them more effectively;
- Outline the key business challenges African DIHs face;
- Understand the basic concepts of project management;
- Design a strategic plan.

5.3.3 Delivery Methods

- Seminar-style presentations;
- Group discussions;
- Hands-on work;
- Take home tasks to complete before/ after the workshop;
- Case studies;
- Work in groups.

5.3.4 Teaching Materials

- PowerPoint presentations;

- Examples from case studies;
- Useful templates;
- Best practices examples from DIH.

These materials shall be prepared by local facilitators and uploaded onto the online repository.

5.3.5 Activity Plan

Activity	Mins	Facilitation / Delivery Method
Workshop Title: Purpose-driven DIH		
Motivate	5	Video/ice breaker
House Keeping	10	Expectations, timetable, how the course will run, etc
Topic 1: Setting the scene for DIH <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purpose • Role • Processes 	60	Delivery will include seminar-style presentation; group discussions; etc.)
Group Activity	15	Hands-on work
Break	20	
Topic 2: DIH Activity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key business challenges • Project Management • Strategic planning 	100	Delivery will include seminar-style presentation; group discussions; etc.)
Group Activity	30	Hands-on work
Total Time for Workshop	240	4h (for example, a whole morning)

5.3.6 Assessment

At the end of the course, each participant should be able to address the following questions:

1. Why is it beneficial to have a clear purpose, role and processes?
2. What are the key business challenges?
3. What are the main project management steps?
4. How to design a strategic plan?

5.3.7 Training Exercise

Participants will be invited to select any of their impending projects or a project that they are already working on and use the Gantt Chart template on the online

repository to order their activities against time, responsible personnel and expected deliverables.

6. Conclusion

The local workshops will help the African DIHs to build their capacities to support the start-ups they work with. Even though the D2.1 indicated that the African DIH prefer face-to-face workshops, this may not be fully achieved due to the pandemic and possible lockdowns. Hence, we have proposed a blend of face-to-face and virtual workshops. More so, the blended approach will help to reach out to many DIHs who may not have had the opportunity to participate in the training because of distance.

It is also anticipated that the workshop will be more appealing to the African DIH participants since the content caters for the African context. The opportunity to be mentored by experienced DIHs in Europe will also be an additional motivation for some hubs to participate in the workshops. The European DIHs that will work with the African DIHs will also have the opportunity to access markets and other opportunities in the African ecosystem.

7. References

Below are reference materials for further learning. The materials are grouped under the titles of the various workshops. Learning materials for workshops that are not listed here can be found on the online repository. Supplementary materials that shall be developed by the local facilitators will also be uploaded to the online repository and made accessible to all.

DIH Strategy and Strategy Resources

- The Art of Strategy: A Game Theorist's Guide to Success in Business and Life by Avinash K. Dixit and Barry J. Nalebuff
- Good Strategy/Bad Strategy: The Difference and Why It Matters (Roughcut) by Richard Rumelt
- The Economist: Business Strategy 3rd edition: A guide to effective decision-making by Jeremy Kourdi
- The Strategy Book 2e: How to think and act strategically to deliver outstanding results by Max Mckeown
- 16 Strategic Planning Models to Consider.

DIH Business Model

- The Concept of a Business Model by B. Hill
- How to Design a Winning Business Model by R. Casadesus-Masanell, J. Ricart
- Business model Generation by Osterwalder A., Pigneur Y
- The Business Model Navigator: 55 Models that Will Revolutionise Your Business by Gassmann, O., Frankenberger, K., Csik, M.
- The PPP Canvas
- Business models for Digital Innovation Hubs in the agriculture and food domain by Alliance for the Internet of Things innovation: <https://aioti.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/20180914-AIOTI-ADIHs-survey-results-vfinal.pdf>

Draft a Preliminary Business Model for your DIHs

- [Business Model Toolbox](#)
- [Three Levels of Business Models](#)
- The Cambridge Business Model Innovation Process by Gleissdoerfer M., Savaget P., Evans, S.

Bootstrapping, Revenue Models and Managerial Accounting

- [British Council Creative HubKit](#)
- [Afrilabs Learning Week Material](#)
- [Biz4Africa Finance Toolkit](#)

Preparing projects for investment and investor relationships

- DPixel course material: The Perfect Pitch, Term Sheets, Innovation Financing
- [The Finance Toolkit](#)
- [Social Impact Navigator](#)
- [Afrilabs Hubs Learning Week financial information](#)

Building and using a network of funding sources

- [ITU Bridging the Digital Innovation Divide](#)
- [British Council Creative Hubkit](#)
- [Afrilabs Hub Learning Week Material](#)